

CLASSIFICATION OF PROVERBS WITH “HORSE” COMPONENT IN UZBEK

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Abstract: Proverbs are formed based on the life, social, and historical experiences of people. A comprehensive study of proverbs from the perspective of their content is directly related to disciplines such as cultural studies, ethnolinguistics, and ethnography. Culture is usually passed from one generation to another through language. In the early stages of social development, this transmission occurred orally, including through folk oral creativity, particularly proverbs, which are among the most prominent genres of such creativity.

Key words: proverb, Uzbek proverbs, horse, component, classification.

In global linguistics, research on the unique characteristics of proverbs is being conducted in the following main directions: examining the diachronic and synchronic states of proverbs and their manifestations in speech; studying proverbs from linguocultural, linguopragmatic, and cognitive perspectives; conducting comparative-typological studies of proverbs across different languages; analyzing proverbs from a psychological perspective; and describing proverbs for didactic and methodological purposes.

In science, the study of proverbs as an object of folk oral creativity, ethnography, and linguistics, as well as their scientific-theoretical analysis within the idiom-phrase-proverb system, has a long history. Significant results have been achieved in linguistic research within this field, where proverbs began to be studied primarily as fixed expressions, specifically as part of idioms. This led to the development of narrow and broad perspectives on the study of phraseology.

In Uzbek linguistics, the scientific study of expressions, idioms, proverbs, and sayings as objects of phraseology has been a focus of research,¹ in many studies,

¹ Данияров А. Стилистические функции синонимов в современном узбекском языке: Автореф. дис. ... канд. филол. наук. – Самарканд, 1967. – 18 с.; Саломов Ф. Бадий таржиманинг лексик-фразеологик масалалари: Филол. фан. ном. ... дис. – Тошкент, 1964. – 124 б.; Тил ва таржима. – Тошкент: Фан, 1966. – 384 б.; Рузикулова М. Идиоматика узбекского языка: Автореф. дис. ... канд. филол. наук. – Самарканд, 1966. – С. 22; Каххарова Х. Фразеология Абдуллы Кадыри: Автореф. дис. ... канд. филол. наук. – Ташкент, 1985. – 24 с.; Маматов А.Э. Ҳозирги замон ўзбек адабий тилида лексик ва фразеологик норма муаммолари. – Тошкент: Фан, 1991. – 274 б.; Йўлдошев Б. Ҳозирги

including candidate and doctoral dissertations, significant attention has been given to exploring the semantic and stylistic features of proverbs in the language and style of works by Uzbek writers and poets.²

In B. Abdushukurov's candidate dissertation, the zoonymic terms used in Turkic written sources created between the 11th and 14th centuries were analyzed from lexical-semantic, functional-semantic, and structural-grammatical perspectives. This research is significant in identifying the semantic groups of zonyms within the Turkic lexical corpus.³

Proverbs reflect the history, traditions, beliefs, culture, worldview, and lifestyle of a people. Proverbs containing the “horse” component do not solely discuss the animal itself; they can also be interpreted figuratively. These proverbs often carry layers of meaning with educational significance. For example: *Yomon otga yol bitsa, yoniga tursuq boylatmas* (arrogance, conceit, fulfillment); *Ot bo'lsang, choparsan, It bo'lsang, qoparsan* (dexterity, responsibility); *Ot bilan tepishgan toyning engagi sinar* (behaving age-appropriately, not being equal to adults); *Yolg'iz otning changi*

Ўзбек адабий тилида фразеологик бирликларнинг функционал-услубий хусусиятлари: Филол. фан. док. ... дис. автореф. – Тошкент, 1993. – 50 б.

² Назарова Х. Ҳ.Ҳ. Ниёзий асарларининг тили: Филол. фан. ном. ... дис. – Тошкент, 1944. – 114 б.; Шоабдурахмонов Ш. “Равшан” поэмаси тилининг бадиий хусусиятлари: Филол. фан. ном. ... дис. – Тошкент, 1949. – 128 б.; Ойбек романларининг тили ва стили // Шарқ юлдузи. – Тошкент, 1955. №10; Пинхасов Я. Фразеологические выражения в языке произведений Хаида Алимджана: Автореф. дис. ... канд. филол. наук. – Ташкент, 1953. – 18 с.; Ўзбек тили фразеологияси ҳақида. – Тошкент: Ўқитувчи, 1957. – 27 б.; Шомаксудов А. Язык сатиры Мукуми (лексика и фразеология): Автореф. дис. ... канд. филол. наук. – Ташкент, 1956. – 18 с.; Абдуллаев В., Дониёров Х., Мирзаев С. Шиддаткор одамлар қиссаси // Шарқ юлдузи. – Тошкент, 1960. №2. – Б. 115–122; Хусаинов М. Фразеология прозы писательницы Айдын: Автореф. дис. ... канд. филол. наук. – Самарқанд, 1959. – 18 с.; Дониёров Х., Мирзаев С. Сўз санъати (Маҳорат ва тил ҳақида мулоҳазалар). – Тошкент: Ўзадабийнашр, 1962; Қўчқортоев И. А. Қаҳорнинг фразеологик маҳорати: Филол. фан. ном. ... дис. – Тошкент, 1965. – 134 б.; Самадов Қ. Ойбек – сўз санъаткори. – Тошкент, 1965. – 24 б.; Абдуллаев О. Эмоционально-экспрессивная лексика в современной узбекской прозе (по роману Абдуллы Каххара “Огни Кошчинара”): Автореф. дис. ... канд. филол. наук. – Самарқанд, 1968. – 20 с.; Азизхонова Л. “Навоий” романидаги фразеологизмларнинг рус тилига таржимаси // Ўзбек тили ва адабиёти. – Тошкент, 1970. №3. – Б. 54–57; Асқаров С. А. Қодирий ижодида фольклорнинг баъзи масалалари // Ўзбек тили ва адабиёти. – Тошкент, 1973. №1. – Б. 19–22; Жўрахонов А. Муқимийнинг халқ мақолларидан фойдаланиш маҳорати // Ўзбек тили ва адабиёти. – Тошкент, 1974. №4. – Б. 52–55; Тўйчиев М. “Шинелли йиллар” романида халқ мақоллари ва ибораларининг ишлатилиши / Ўзбек фразеологиясидан тадқиқотлар. СамДПИ асарлари. – Самарқанд, 1971. – Б. 84–87; Ҳакимов М. Ёзувчи ва халқ тили. – Тошкент: Фан, 1971. – 176 б. 1. Абдурахмонов Х. Синтаксические особенности узбекских народных пословиц: Автореф. дис. ... канд. филол. наук. – Ташкент: АН УзССР, 1964. – 18 с.; Абдурахмонов Х. Особенности синтаксиса узбекского устного народного творчества: Автореф. дис. ... док. филол. наук. – Ташкент, 1977. – 48 с.; Садриддинова М. Лексика узбекских пословиц и поговорок: Автореф. дис. ... канд. филол. наук. – Ташкент, 1985. – 18 с.; Жўраева Б. Мақолларнинг лисоний мавқеи ва маъновий-услубий қўлланилиши: Филол. фан. ном. ... дис. автореф. – Самарқанд, 2002. – 24 б.; Бакиров П. У. Номинацентрические пословицы в разносистемных языках (на материале русского, узбекского и казахского языков): Дис. ... док. филол. наук. – Тошкент, 2007. – 286 с.

³ Абдушукуров Б. Б. XI–XIV аср туркий ёзма манбалар тилидаги зоонимлар. Филол. фанлари номзоди.... дисс. – Тошкент, 1998.

chiqmas, Changi chiqsa ham, dong‘i chiqmas (calling for unity, the harm of acting alone); *Ahmoq otdan tushsa ham, Egardan tushmas* (stubbornness, non-interference) and so on.

In the study, the collection of “Uzbek folk proverbs” containing more than 13,000 proverbs was analyzed, and it was found that there are 266 proverbs with a “horse” component, and they were classified into 35 thematic groups. They are as follows:

1. Proverbs with the “horse” component on the topic of laziness, apathy:

Sansolar-u mansolar, otga yemni kim solar; Erinchoq eshikka chiqsa, ot yollaydi.

2. Proverbs with the “horse” component on the topic of arrogance and boasting:

Yomon otga yol bitsa, yoniga tursuq boylatmas; Yomon otni maqtagan yo‘lda qolar.

3. Proverbs with the “horse” component on the topic of intelligence and ignorance:

Aqllining oti ham horimas, to‘ni ham tozimas; Ahmoq otdan tushsa ham, egardan tushmas.

4. Proverbs with the “horse” component on the subject of bravery and cowardice:

Alp – enadan, tulpor – biyadan; Ot hurkkan yeridan otmas, Er – qo‘rqan yeridan.

5. Proverbs with the “horse” component on the topic of equality and inequality:

Ikki ot tepishsa, O‘rtada eshak olar; Ot tepkisini ot ko‘tarar.

6. Proverbs with the “horse” component on the topic of hard work:

Aravani ot tortar, Ko‘lankasini it; Yorga otning yo‘li bor, Jo‘rtoqining sho‘ri bor.

7. Proverbs with the “horse” component on the topic of acquiring knowledge and skills:

Ilm – egarlangan ot, Bilganga – do‘st, bilmaganga – yov; Hunar to‘ygizar, Ot mindirib, to‘n kiygizar.

8. Proverbs with the “horse” component on the subject of courage and bravery:

Ot kuchini karvonda ko‘r, Mard kuchin – maydonda; Otni ham maydonda sina, Erni ham maydonda sina.

9. Proverbs with the “horse” component on the subject of education and custom:

Otning fe‘li egasiga ma‘lum; Ayg‘ir qanday bo‘lsa, ot shunday.

10. Proverbs with the “horse” component on the topic of beauty and ugliness:

Otni yaxshi ko‘rsatgan – Tuyoqdagi taqasi; Yigit ko‘rki – ot-yarog‘

11. Proverbs with the “horse” component on the topic of humility and arrogance:

Ot ko‘rmagan ot ko‘rsa, Otxonada ot chopar; Ot mingan otasini tanimas, Toy mingan – og‘asini.

12. Proverbs with the “horse” component related to the theme of the road:

Olis yo‘l otni sinar, Og‘ir yo‘l mardni sinar; Oting borida yo‘l tani, Esing borida el tani.

- 13. Proverbs with the “horse” component on the topic of old age:** *Ot qarisa – oxurda, It qarisa – chuqurda; It qarisa, qopolmas, Ot qarisa, chopolmas.*
- 14. Proverbs with the “horse” component on the topic of satisfaction and regret:** *Minmasang ham, ot yaxshi, Quchmasang ham, qiz yaxshi; Otga minolmagan uzangidan o‘pkalar.*
- 15. Proverbs with the “horse” component on the topic of caution and vigilance:** *It qopmas, Ot tepmas dema; Avval otingni taqala, Keyin yo‘l tanla.*
- 16. Proverbs with the “horse” component on the topic of well-being and abundance:** *Ot bo‘lsa, maydon topilar, Ot bo‘lmasa, maydon chopilar; Arpa yegan ot o‘ynar, Makka yegan tot o‘ynar.*
- 17. Proverbs with the “horse” component on the topic of using the correct action:** *Daryoga ot solmasdan avval kechuvini top; Bir mix bir nag‘alni, Bir nag‘al bir otni tutar.*
- 18. Proverbs with the “horse” component on the topic of good and bad:** *Yomonning oti bilan uloq olguncha, Yaxshining eshagida otquloq ol; Yomonga el bo‘lguncha, Yag‘ir otga bel bo‘l.*
- 19. Proverbs with the “horse” component on the topic of entrepreneurship and idleness:** *Ot mingan olisni ko‘zlar; Bekor otning boshi o‘tlar, Bog‘liq bo‘lsa, yaxshi o‘tlar.*
- 20. Proverbs with the “horse” component on the topic of profit and loss:** *Yomonga el bo‘lguncha, Yag‘ir otga bel bo‘l.*
- 21. Proverbs with the “horse” component on the topic of weakness:** *Arpasiz ot dovon osholmas; Oriq otga qamchi ham yuk.*
- 22. Proverbs with the “horse” component on the topic of working with a plan:** *Ot minib yaqinni ko‘zlaguncha, Tuya minib uzoqni ko‘zla; Ot minsang, olisni ko‘zla.*
- 23. Proverbs with the “horse” component on the topic of need and necessity:** *Yo‘qni kerak toptirar, Yolg‘iz otni sottirar; Otni topish bir kunlik, Abzal topish ming kunlik.*
- 24. Adverbs with the “horse” component related to the advantage of owning one's own thing:** *O‘zganing otidan, O‘zingning eshaging yaxshi; Kishanli ot – o‘z oting, Tushovli ot – bo‘z oting.*
- 25. Proverbs with the “horse” component on the subject of thrift:** *Otni ayagan ot minar, To‘nni ayagan to‘n kiyar.*
- 26. Proverbs with the “horse” component on the topic of sustenance:** *Otlining nasibasi – oltov, Tuyalining nasibasi – to‘rtov; Ot bosmagan yerlarni toy bosar.*

27. Proverbs with the “horse” component on the subject of cause and effect: *Ot oriqlasa, tuvaloq bo‘lar; Ot tortishib ot tanir, Er tortishib – el.*

28. Proverbs with the “horse” component on the subject of prudence and imprudence: *Chala tentak otini maqtar, Toza tentak – xotinini; Aravani ot oldiga chiqarib bo‘lmas.*

29. Proverbs with the “horse” component on the theme of harmony: *Og‘a-ini totuv bo‘lsa, ot ko‘p, Opa-singil totuv bo‘lsa, osh ko‘p.*

30. Proverbs with the “horse” component on the topic of trust and distrust: *Bir minarga ot berma; Andizli yerda ot o‘lmas, Iyirli yerda – er.*

31. Proverbs with the “horse” component on the subject of greed: *Ot ko‘rmagan ot ko‘rsa, Mina-mina o‘ldirar; Yemxo‘r ot to‘rva teshar.*

32. Proverbs with the “horse” component on the subject of experience: *Oy minmay, otingni maqtama, Yil turmay – xotiningni; Ot minsang o‘ylab uzoqni, Bilib yur yo‘ldagi tuzoqni.*

33. Proverbs with the “horse” component on the topic of kinship and alienation: *Oziqli ot horimas, Qarindoshli qarimas; Begonaning oti o‘zguncha, Ovuldoshingning toyi o‘zsin.*

34. Proverbs with the “horse” component on the topic of neighborhood: *Ovuldoshimning oti o‘zguncha, Hamsoyamning toyi o‘zsin.*

35. Proverbs with the “horse” component on the theme of patriotism: *El – qo‘ngan yerda, Ot – to‘ygan yerda; El qo‘ngan yerni bilar, Ot to‘ygan yerda tinar.*

Recommendations on how to behave in various situations in life, social judgments have been living in our proverbs for centuries. In the proverbs, it is possible to see that the behavior of people is described in an impressive way, social judgments, subtle aspects of human nature and psyche are reflected, and advice is given. The genre of folk oral creativity that is unique as a “Guide to Upbringing” characterized by its brevity yet profound impact — proverbs — is an unparalleled example of the artistic wisdom of our ancestors. Its significance lies in its ability to reveal the characteristics of specific periods in our language and literature.

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